

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MANIFESTATION OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENTS

¹Shomurotov U.M., ²Yoldoshev T.A.

¹Teacher at the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Denov Entrepreneurship and
Pedagogy Institute

²Senior Teacher at the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Denov Entrepreneurship and
Pedagogy Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14442418>

Abstract. *This article explores the psychological characteristics of aggressive behavior in adolescents, highlighting the multifaceted nature of this complex issue. It examines key factors influencing aggression, including impulsivity, emotional regulation, cognitive distortions, and the impact of social influences such as peer dynamics and media exposure. By integrating various psychological theories—from early psychoanalytic perspectives to contemporary cognitive-behavioral and ecological models—the article provides a comprehensive overview of how these elements interact to manifest aggression during adolescence. Furthermore, it discusses the implications for intervention and prevention strategies, emphasizing the need for holistic approaches that address the underlying psychological processes. This synthesis of research aims to enhance understanding and inform effective practices to support adolescents in managing aggressive behaviors.*

Keywords: *emotional intensity, social dynamics, aggression, anxiety, biological factor, cognitive factor, human instinct.*

Aggressive behavior in adolescents is a complex phenomenon that has garnered significant attention from psychologists, educators, and researchers. Understanding the psychological characteristics underlying this behavior is crucial, as adolescence is a critical developmental stage marked by heightened emotional intensity and social dynamics. The interplay of biological, cognitive, and environmental factors contributes to the manifestation of aggression, making it essential to explore how impulsivity, emotional regulation, peer influence, and cognitive distortions shape these behaviors. As society continues to evolve, so too does the understanding of adolescent aggression, necessitating effective interventions and support systems to address this issue in a holistic manner.

The study of aggressive behavior in adolescents has evolved significantly over the years, reflecting changes in psychological theory, research methodologies, and societal understanding.

Early Theories date back to Pre-20th Century. Ancient philosophers like Aristotle discussed the nature of aggression, often linking it to human instincts and moral behavior. Theories emerged suggesting that aggression was an inherent trait, influenced by physical and genetic factors.

Psychoanalytic Theories were developed in early 20th Century. One of them is Freud's Drive Theory. Sigmund Freud posited that aggression is a fundamental human drive, akin to sexual instincts. He suggested that unresolved inner conflicts could lead to aggressive behavior.

Aggression was seen as a response to anxiety, where individuals might project their feelings onto others.

Behaviorism emerged mid-20th Century. Behaviorists like B.F. Skinner emphasized the role of environmental factors and reinforcement in shaping aggressive behaviors. Aggression was viewed as a learned response to specific stimuli. Albert Bandura's work highlighted the importance of observational learning, suggesting that adolescents could learn aggression by watching others, notably in media.

Late 20th century researchers began to explore how adolescents' thoughts and interpretations of social situations could lead to aggressive responses. Misinterpretation of cues was identified as a significant factor. The focus shifted to understanding how emotional factors, such as anger management and frustration tolerance, contributed to aggressive behavior.

Urie Bronfenbrenner's model emphasized the interplay between individual traits and environmental contexts, including family, peers, and societal influences in current studies. Advances in neuroscience revealed how developmental changes in the adolescent brain, particularly the prefrontal cortex, affect impulse control and aggression.

Contemporary research considers a combination of biological, psychological, and social factors, recognizing the complexity of aggressive behavior. There is a growing focus on developing prevention and intervention strategies that address the underlying psychological factors contributing to aggression. The study of aggressive behavior in adolescents has transitioned from simplistic views of inherent traits to a nuanced understanding that incorporates cognitive, emotional, and environmental factors. Ongoing research continues to explore this multifaceted issue, aiming to inform effective interventions.

One of the pressing issues that interests not only psychologists but also sociologists, attorneys, educators, philosophers, social workers, and leaders at all levels is the state of affairs brought on by hostility or disputes between individuals. Children's development of a healthy lifestyle and environmental education are negatively impacted by aggressive events, particularly when they involve children. We think it's important to bring school-family cooperation back into the spotlight.

One of the major and pressing issues facing the sciences is the study of the laws governing the link between mental development and the processes that bring about these changes. According to Australian psychologist K. Buhler, a child's moral development is influenced by their generational perspective in addition to their intellectual development. Human nature cannot be altered; a person is born with the needs and mental traits shaped by their genetic makeup, according to American psychologist and educator D. Dewey. According to him, the degree of education is determined by these demands and mental traits, which are expressed during the educational process and occasionally alter.

According to the biogenetic doctrine, a student's abilities and capabilities are assessed through special tests, and his genetic makeup then determines the educational process. The level of human ability development (for instance, the limit of capabilities, its highest point) is determined by fate. They stress the importance of adjusting to one's developmental stage and attending schools that correspond to one's degree of intellectual aptitude. According to American psychologist E. Thorndike, who is one of the proponents of this approach, pupils' "natural powers" and "innate inclinations" are the primary drivers of mental growth, with the environment and school having a secondary impact.

Adolescent violent behavior has a unique characteristic that can be described by its association with the peer group and the context of adult authority. Aggression at this age is defined as "being strong or appearing strong". Every youth organization with a leader has its own stories and legends. Membership offers, for instance, are frequently made (or testing new arrivals). A prominent group known as "uniform"—a generic teen fashion trend—has traditional character. Teenagers' activities in life are still based on beliefs, which also help them feel secure and like they belong to a community. Many times, in-group and out-group aggression are justified by myths.

The way an adolescent displays aggression depends on his family environment, peer group, macroenvironment (school), the norms and traditions of his community, and the kind of knowledge that is available to him. In this, the family is very important. It covers the way spouses treat one another, the parent-child relationship, the family's moral standards, the worldview, and the family's aims and objectives.

The psychological characteristics of aggressive behavior in adolescents can include:

1. "Impulsivity": Adolescents may act on impulse without considering the consequences, leading to aggressive outbursts.

2. "Emotional Regulation": Difficulty in managing emotions can result in heightened aggression, especially in stressful situations.

3. "Social Influences": Peer pressure and the desire for acceptance can drive adolescents to display aggressive behavior to fit in or assert dominance.

4. "Low Self-Esteem": Some adolescents may exhibit aggression as a defense mechanism to mask insecurities or feelings of inadequacy.

5. "Frustration and Anger Management": Frustration from unmet needs or goals can lead to aggressive responses if they lack healthy coping strategies.

6. "Modeling Behavior": Exposure to aggressive role models, whether at home or in media, can influence adolescents to mimic such behaviors.

7. "Cognitive Distortions": Misinterpretation of social cues or situations can lead to inappropriate aggressive responses.

8. "Mental Health Issues": Conditions such as ADHD, anxiety, or depression can contribute to aggressive tendencies.

Understanding these characteristics can help in developing effective interventions and support systems for adolescents exhibiting aggressive behavior. In summary, frustration is the primary cause of aggression. All of the challenges that keep you from reaching your objectives are sources of frustration. The manifestation of aggressive behavior in adolescents is deeply rooted in a combination of psychological, social, and biological factors. This multifaceted nature underscores the importance of understanding the specific characteristics that contribute to aggression, such as impulsivity, emotional regulation, and cognitive distortions. Recognizing the role of environmental influences, including peer relationships and societal expectations, is essential for developing effective interventions.

As research continues to evolve, it is imperative to adopt holistic approaches that not only address the behaviors themselves but also support adolescents in building healthier coping mechanisms and emotional resilience. By fostering a deeper understanding of the psychological underpinnings of aggression, we can better equip young people to navigate their emotions and

social interactions, ultimately reducing the prevalence of aggressive behavior and promoting positive development.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The rule of law is the guarantee of the development of human interests and the well-being of the people. "Uzbekistan", 2017.5.
2. L.M. Semenyuk "Psychological characteristics of aggressive behavior6.podrostkov i usloviya ego korrektsii» Moscow, 1996 96th st.7.
3. R. Beron D. Richardson –Aggression spb 1997. 104 st.8.
4. K.Yu Gulyaeva "Agressivenessin adolescent age and correction" UDK159.96+159.94+316.6 23.12.2006g.9.
5. Ilesheva R.G. Narusheniya povedeniya u detey i podrostkov.–Alma-Ata: Nauka,1990. -160 st.10.
6. Yunusova, Guzal Sultanovna. «Razvitie voobrazheniya molodeji I podrostkov, vospityvayushchikhsya blagopoluchnyx i neblagopoluchnyx semyax».Theoretical & Applied Science 6 (2013): 91-94
7. Aggression in Adolescents: The Role of Mother-Child Attachment and SelfEsteemPMC(<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9137955/>)n
8. Assessing and treating aggression in children and adolescents - Adesanya-PediatricMedicine(<https://pm.amegroups.org/article/view/6186/html>)
9. Personality traits and aggressive behavior in adolescents | PRBM(<https://www.dovepress.com/personality-traits-and-aggressive-behavior-in-vietnamese-adolescents-peer-reviewed-fulltext-article-PRBM>)